

Geophysics

1 FLOW-INDUCED ALTERATIONS OF ULTRASONIC SIGNATURES AND FRACTURE
2 APERTURE UNDER CONSTANT STATE-OF-STRESS IN A SINGLE-FRACTURED ROCK
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ABSTRACT

Fluid-fracture surface interactions, caused by different mechanisms, is one of the underlying reasons for permeability reduction over long periods of time in different geo-resources, such as deep geothermal systems and shale gas/oil reservoirs. The sensitivity of the ultrasonic signatures (e.g. frequency content, velocity, amplitude, and attenuation) to the changes in fracture aperture caused by fluid-fracture surface interactions can be considered as a probe for flow-induced fracture aperture evolution. Flow-through tests on an artificially-fractured phyllite specimen from a geothermal reservoir along with the concurrent measurements of ultrasonic signatures of P- and cross-polarized S-waves demonstrated the sensitivity of ultrasonic signatures to the evolution of fracture aperture/permeability under constant state-of-stress (i.e. constant pore and confining pressures). Particularly, the closure of fracture and decrease of permeability led to increase of P-wave velocity, decrease of P-wave attenuation, and increase of S-waves amplitude. In addition, time evolution of the time-frequency maps of the transmitted ultrasonic waves revealed that the partitioning of the frequency content slightly changes, as the fracture aperture/permeability is altered. Specifically, alterations in hydraulic aperture is reflected in the changes of time-frequency partitioning, while, under constant hydraulic aperture, the time-frequency partitioning is unaltered.

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INTRODUCTION

Characterizing the aperture size and distribution during operation of fractured reservoirs is a challenging task, and often it is necessary to study the evolution of fracture permeability as it significantly influences reservoir production in geothermal, shale gas, and tight oil reservoirs. The geometry of fracture surface area substantially affects the fracture response and therefore

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56 production of fractured reservoirs through different mechanisms/phenomena such as pressure
57 solution (e.g. Kamali-Asl et al., 2018a), mineral dissolution/precipitation (e.g. Faoro et al.,
58 2016), and mechanical creep (e.g. Sone and Zoback, 2013b). Fracture surface roughness and
59 tortuosity of asperities of the rock joints/fractures control the mechanical deformation, while,
60 hydraulic properties (i.e. flow properties) are controlled by aperture size (Cook, 1992; Pyrak-
61 Nolte and Morris, 2000; Acosta-Colon et al., 2009). Important to note, aperture distribution
62 along a fracture, amount and spatial distribution of the asperities, and contact area of the fracture
63 can influence both fracture-specific stiffness and flow through the fracture (Pyrak-Nolte and
64 Morris, 2000). More specifically, uneven distribution of aperture along a fracture can result in
65 larger aperture along the major flow path and/or in critical necks, which in turn leads to higher
66 permeability (e.g. Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte, 2016). Larger aperture, and therefore larger volume of
67 void space, creates more compliant fractures with the same contact area (e.g. Pyrak-Nolte and
68 Nolte, 2016). Since reservoir production is affected by fracture aperture/permeability, it is
69 important to monitor the long-term evolution of fracture aperture over the reservoir's operation
70 period.

71 Seismic waves can be considered as high-resolution probes to assess the alteration of
72 fractures/joints in fractured formations, as they are sensitive to different elements of geological
73 formations (e.g. overburden and pore pressures, depth of interest, and saturation level) (e.g.
74 Wang, 2001; Knight et al., 2010; Müller et al., 2010; Pyrak-Nolte et al., 2015; Saltiel et al.,
75 2017). Compressional (P-type) and shear (S-type) waves are usually implemented to infer
76 information about the internal structure of intact rocks in different formations such as shale and
77 geothermal reservoirs (e.g. Sayers, 2013; Sone and Zoback, 2013a; Lopes et al., 2014; Kamali-
78 Asl et al., 2018b-d). Propagation of seismic waves in fractured formations gives rise to

79 frequency-dependent elastic interface waves, which exhibit a velocity ranging from shear-wave
80 (upper limit) to Rayleigh-wave (lower limit) (e.g. Pyrak-Nolte et al., 1990; Pyrak-Nolte and
81 Morris, 2000; Batzle et al., 2006). Mechanical deformations at the fracture surface and alteration
82 of hydraulic properties of the fractured formation can significantly affect the seismic response of
83 fractured formations (e.g. Cook, 1992; Mukerji and Mavko, 1994; Mavko, 2009). In addition, a
84 fracture can be weakened/strengthened by the geochemical processes at the fracture surface, and
85 hence, affects the response to shear/slip as well as long-term reservoir production (e.g. Pyrak-
86 Nolte et al., 2015). Therefore, the evolution of the seismic signatures (namely, frequency
87 content, velocity, amplitude, and attenuation) can be used as a proxy to track the evolution of
88 fracture aperture/permeability.

89 In this study, flow-through experiments were performed to investigate the sensitivity of
90 the ultrasonic signatures to the changes in the aperture size resulted from different physio-
91 chemical processes at fracture surface. In a companion paper, the authors have reported the
92 results from a suite of flow-through experiments under varying state-of-stress (i.e. varying
93 confining and/or pore pressures). Here, an artificially-fractured phyllite specimen was used to
94 conduct the flow-through-fracture tests with concurrent measurements of the ultrasonic P- and
95 cross-polarized S-waves, along with radial strains. The transmitted ultrasonic P- and cross-
96 polarized S-waves were then analyzed to infer changes in the fracture aperture using velocities,
97 amplitudes, attenuations, and frequency content of these waves. Section 2 provides the
98 Experimental Methodology, Section 3 provides the Results and Discussions. Conclusions are
99 provided in Section 4.

101 **Specimen preparation**

102 A phyllite rock core, shown in Figure 1(a), was retrieved from DB-2 well (depth of 1260
103 m) at Blue Mountain geothermal field (Nevada, USA) and sub-cored to obtain a rock specimen
104 with a diameter of 38 mm, and a length of 49 mm. The rock had a dry density of 2.69 g/cm³ and
105 porosity of 0.74%. The X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis indicated that the rock contained
106 67.4% quartz, 18.8% albite, 10.5% biotite, and 3.2% chlorite. The specimen was saw-cut, and
107 the two ends were lapped to 0.001 inches. A modified Brazilian test (Yu et al., 2009) was
108 performed to induce a longitudinal tensile fracture in the specimen (Figure 1(a)), with minimal
109 material loss in the fracturing process. The fracture surface was characterized using SkyScan
110 1173 X-Ray micro-CT instrument. Figure 2 shows 3D images of the two halves of the fractured
111 specimen and the generated surface profiles.

112 The fractured specimen was then vacuum-saturated with deionized water. To ensure the
113 full saturation of the specimen, weights were measured every day until the change in weight was
114 equal to or less than 0.005 g (scale precision). The two halves of the saturated fractured specimen
115 were well-mated together, and a copper jacket was wrapped around the fractured specimen to
116 facilitate attachment of the strain gauges. Then the specimen was inserted inside a Viton jacket,
117 with two open cuts at 180°-apart to expose the copper jacket for attachment of the strain gauges.
118 As shown in Figure 1(c), the strain gauges were attached on each half of the specimen. The
119 interface between the Viton and copper jacket was sealed using the high-pressure/temperature-
120 resistant epoxy Loctite EA 608. The fracture plane of the specimen was oriented at ~45° to the
121 plane of propagation of S₁-waves (See Figure 3(b)). Finally, the two ends of the specimen were

122 wire-tightened to the top and bottom ultrasonic velocity core-holders (Figure 1(c)) and the
123 specimen was placed inside the test vessel (Figure 1(d)).

124 **Experimental procedure**

125 A high-pressure/temperature fully servo-controlled triaxial equipment (Autolab 1500,
126 shown in Figure 1(d)), housed in the Porous Media Laboratory at the University of Vermont, was
127 used to perform flow-through test on the fractured phyllite specimen. The instrument is capable
128 of applying a Confining Pressure (CP) and pore pressures of up to 70 MPa and a Differential
129 Stress (DS) of up to 580 MPa (for specimens having a diameter of 38.1 mm) using four separate
130 pressure intensifiers. The instrument enables performing flow-through tests with constant pore
131 pressures (i.e. Pressure-Controlled Test (PCT)), or constant injection rate (i.e. Displacement-
132 Controlled Test (DCT)) with a precision of ± 0.1 MPa and errors of $\pm 0.2\%$.

133 PCT was performed by setting both the upstream and downstream pore pressure
134 intensifiers at a constant pressure to maintain the constant differential pore pressure throughout
135 the test. In PCT, the evolution of the outflow rate was recorded and used to estimate the
136 corresponding permeability and fracture aperture during the test. DCT with a prescribed constant
137 injection rate was performed by setting the downstream pore pressure at a constant value, while
138 the upstream pore pressure intensifier continuously adjusts (i.e. either increases or decreases) the
139 upstream pore pressure to maintain the prescribed constant injection rate. The evolution of
140 differential pore pressure ($\Delta P = P_{P,\text{upstream}} - P_{P,\text{downstream}}$) was used as an indicative of the change
141 in flow rate, or equivalently fracture aperture. During the test, as the flow-induced processes at
142 the fracture surface lead to closure of the fracture, ΔP increases to compensate the closure of
143 fracture to maintain the constant injection rate. Deionized water at room temperature was

144 injected for ~140 to 150 hours during both tests. Since the specimen had very low porosity
145 (0.74%), the matrix is virtually impermeable, and the flow can be assumed to be laminar. Thus,
146 the modified cubic law with parallel plate approximation was used to estimate the fracture
147 aperture (Whiterspoon et al., 1980; Polak et al., 2003; Kamali-Asl et al., 2018a). We
148 acknowledge that the created fracture was not truly planar and that the fluid/fracture surface
149 interactions are not uniform, and therefore the aperture will be variable and possibly dominated
150 by few flow channels. Due to experimental limitation (fracture surface characterization), the
151 variation of asperity geometry was not taken into account for the interpretation of seismic
152 signatures.

153 Concurrent with the flow of deionized water through the fracture, ultrasonic waves of the
154 fractured specimen were collected by transmitting the ultrasonic P-wave and cross-polarized S-
155 waves from the bottom (i.e. upstream) core-holder and receiving the signals using top (i.e.
156 downstream) core-holder. As illustrated in Figure 3(a), the transducers for P, S_1 , and S_2 waves
157 are stacked together and embedded in the hollow-cylindrical-shaped core-holders. Figure 3(b)
158 shows the cross-section of the fractured phyllite specimen and direction of propagation of P- and
159 cross-polarized S-waves.

160 The P, S_1 , and S_2 transducers, manufactured by Boston Piezo-Optics Inc., have
161 thicknesses of 2, 1, and 1 mm, respectively, with a diameter of 22.2 mm. These transducers are
162 all made of PZT5A material, a polarized ceramic-type Lead-Zirconate-Titanate alloy. This
163 material has a crystalline structure, which enables sending the ultrasonic waves in a particular
164 direction. The central frequency of the ultrasonic waves was set to 750 kHz with a pulse
165 generation and acquisition rate of 10 pulses/second. Tektronix TDS 3000 Series Oscilloscope

166 was used as a digitizer. The arrival time of P- and cross-polarized S-waves, which were used for
167 estimation of P- and S-waves velocities (V_P , V_{S1} , and V_{S2}), were manually picked according to
168 ASTM D5777 Standard. The upstream pore pressure was set higher than downstream pore
169 pressure, and therefore, the direction of flow (deionized water) was always from bottom of the
170 fractured specimen to the top, same as the direction of wave propagation. In addition, strain
171 gauges attached to the specimen, capture the evolution of strain as fracture aperture evolves
172 during the experiments.

173 **Experimental program**

174 Previous studies on flow-through experiments on artificially-fractured granite specimens
175 under reservoir conditions, few days long, showed the gradual decrease in permeability/fracture
176 aperture (e.g. Caulk et al., 2016; Kamali-Asl et al., 2018a). Conducting flow-through tests in
177 PCT closely simulates the flow in fractured reservoir conditions, in that, the flow rate (reflecting
178 permeability) usually declines and hence, the production drops over time. However, it is usually
179 easier to perform DCTs in laboratory experiments. In order to (i) investigate repeatability of the
180 results, and (ii) broaden the potential future experimental studies (e.g. elevated temperatures and
181 different depths of interest), a DCT was also performed. The differential pore pressure in PCT
182 and injection rate in DCT were set such that the injected fluid would have enough residence time
183 to react with the surface and thus, the evolutions of permeability/fracture aperture and ultrasonic
184 signatures can be captured.

185 In this study, both types of flow-through tests (i.e. PCT and DCT) were performed on a
186 fractured phyllite specimen at room temperature, under constant CP, DS, and pore pressures of
187 24, 6, and 11 MPa, respectively. These stresses were chosen to represent the in-situ stress

210 In order to verify that presence of fracture leads to alterations of ultrasonic waves, the P-,
211 S₁-, and S₂-waves were measured for an intact phyllite specimen (extracted from the same core,
212 with the identical dimensions as fractured rock) under CP of 30 MPa. The waveforms of the
213 ultrasonic waves were compared with those of fractured specimen under CP and pore pressures
214 of 30 and 11 MPa. Figure 4 shows waveforms for all three ultrasonic waves for intact and
215 fractured specimens, indicating changes in velocities, amplitudes, frequency contents due to
216 presence of fracture and fluid flow. The P-wave arrival time for fractured specimen is less than
217 that of intact specimen, and the amplitude of S-waves become meaningful for fractured specimen
218 compared to very low amplitudes for intact specimen. In addition, the frequency content of the
219 P-wave signals for intact and fractured specimens are slightly different after t=25 □Sec.

220 **Pressure-Controlled Test (PCT)**

221 *Radial strains*

222 Figure 5 shows the evolutions of the average radial strains, flow rate, and the
223 corresponding permeability/fracture aperture (estimated using Darcy's Law/Modified Cubic Law
224 based on flow rate) during PCT under CP, DS, and pore pressures of 24, 6, and 11 MPa,
225 respectively. The apparent permeabilities of $\sim 10^{-19}$ m² suggest that the two halves of the fracture
226 are very well-mated, and they are close to full-contact. It can be observed that during the first 60
227 hours of the test, the radial strain is increasing as the flow rate is decreasing. Different hydro-
228 chemo-mechanical processes (e.g. stress corrosion, pressure solution, and mineral
229 dissolution/precipitation) triggered by fluid-fracture surface interactions under specified stress
230 conditions lead to decrease in fracture aperture and flow rate (e.g. Caulk et al., 2016; Faoro et al.,
231 2016; Kamali-Asl et al., 2018a), as the two halves of the fractured specimen come together, and

232 therefore, the radial strain increases. It should be, however, noted that between $t=64$ to 96 hr, the
233 evolution of radial strain cannot be explained based on the evolution of flow rate, which might
234 be due to an experimental error, where, the upstream pore pressure increased for a few hours,
235 leading to a sudden increase in the flow rate at $t=68$ hr. While, the radial strain data showed a
236 gradual decrease over time, rather than a sudden decrease at $t=68$ hr. After $t=100$ hr, the radial
237 strain can successfully capture the response of the fracture (i.e. flow rate), indicating an
238 increasing overall trend in the radial strain.

239 *Ultrasonic velocities, amplitudes, and attenuations*

240 Figure 6 shows the evolutions of the measured ultrasonic velocities along with flow rate
241 and the corresponding fracture aperture/permeability during PCT. As stated by Gu (1994),
242 propagation of P-waves parallel to the fracture plane leads to the generation of a compressional-
243 type interface wave by the shear particle displacement. Roy and Pyrak-Nolte (1997) and Nolte et
244 al. (2000) have reported changes in the characteristics of the arrival P-wave, propagating along
245 the fracture plane, as the state of the fracture is altered. In addition, creation of secondary micro-
246 cracks, caused by fracture creation in the Brazilian test, can in part explain the sensitivity of the
247 P-wave velocities. A correspondence between the flow rate/aperture and P-wave velocities (with
248 blue and orange ovals for P-wave velocity and flow rate, respectively) can be observed in Figure
249 6(a), where they follow each other with a reverse trend during the test. When the flow rate
250 increases, due to fluid-fracture surface interactions, the P-wave velocity decreases, and vice
251 versa. However, there is a lag between the instances of increase/decrease of flow
252 rate/aperture/permeability compared to decrease/increase of P-wave velocity. That is, when
253 physical changes/processes occur at the fracture surface, P-wave velocity reacts immediately,

254 while, the flow rate/aperture/permeability react at a later time. For cases where the variation in
255 flow rate/aperture is steeper, the change in P-wave velocity is more significant, indicating the
256 sensitivity of P-wave velocity to alterations of fracture surface geometry. On the other hand, rock
257 shifting (due to crushing of contacting asperities), channelized flow, and creation/closure of flow
258 channels can have different impact on flow rate and P-wave velocity, and in part might explain
259 some of the observed inconsistencies/lags between the trends of flow rate and those of P-wave
260 velocity. Figure 6(b) shows the time evolutions of S₁- and S₂-waves velocities and flow
261 rate/aperture/permeability, with no identified viable trend for S₁- and S₂-waves velocities. It
262 appears that alterations of flow rate/aperture/permeability cannot be captured using S-waves
263 velocities. The propagation of the S-wave in the direction parallel to fracture has been found to
264 be insensitive to the state of the fracture, however, the characteristics of S-wave in the direction
265 perpendicular to the fracture plane is affected by the state of the fracture (e.g. Roy and Pyrak-
266 Nolte, 1995; Nolte et al., 2000). In this study, the fracture plane was placed 45° with respect to
267 the propagation direction of each of the two cross-polarized S-waves, and therefore, both S-
268 waves have parallel and perpendicular components to the fracture plane. This can, in part,
269 explain the observed weak correspondence between differential pore pressure and S-waves
270 velocities.

271 The maximum amplitudes of the collected P-, S₁-, and S₂-waves at each time instance
272 were analyzed and normalized with respect to their initial value. Figure 7 shows the time
273 evolutions of the normalized maximum amplitude of the P-, S₁-, and S₂-waves, flow rate, and the
274 corresponding fracture aperture/permeability. As it can be seen in Figure 7, the normalized
275 maximum amplitude of the P-wave is not sensitive to the changes in flow
276 rate/aperture/permeability, in contrast to the normalized maximum amplitudes of S₁- and S₂-

277 waves, where an increasing trend can be observed in Figure 7. This could be potentially
278 attributed to the fact that the impedance (density times velocity) of water compared to that of the
279 rock matrix is much lower and therefore, the shear-wise propagation of shear waves is affected
280 by the ratio of the impedance of the two media, however, the longitudinal-wise propagation of
281 compressional wave is not affected by the impedance ratio between rock matrix and water. The
282 attenuation analysis for the fractured specimen was performed following the procedure outlined
283 in Pyrak-Nolte et al. (1990), as expressed in Eq. (1):

$$Q = -\pi f x / [c \ln(A/A_1)] \quad (1)$$

284 where, Q is the ultrasonic quality factor, f is the central frequency of the transmitted ultrasonic
285 wave, x is the length of the specimen (i.e. fractured rock), c is the phase velocity of the ultrasonic
286 wave, A and A₁ are the maximum spectral amplitudes of the fractured rock and aluminum
287 specimen (with identical dimensions as fractured rock specimen), respectively. For each
288 recorded ultrasonic wave, the Fourier transform was performed on the entire time-series to
289 estimate the maximum spectral amplitude. Figure 8(a) shows the time evolutions of the
290 attenuation factor (1/Q) for P-wave, flow rate, and the corresponding fracture
291 aperture/permeability in PCT, indicating slightly decreasing trend. This observation implies that
292 P-wave attenuation could also serve as a proxy for changes in fracture aperture over time.
293 However, the variations of S₁- and S₂-waves attenuations against flow rate/aperture/permeability
294 over time, as shown in Figure 8(b), do not exhibit an identifiable trend, which indicate that the S-
295 waves attenuation is not sensitive to the changes in fracture aperture.

296 *Time-frequency analysis*

297 **P-wave signals.** Time-frequency analysis of the P-, S₁-, and S₂-waves can reveal
298 information about their time-dependent frequency content. A Continuous Wavelet Transform
299 (CWT), with Morlet Mother Wavelet, was employed to generate time-frequency maps. It should
300 be noted that CWT is a more robust approach compared to short-time-Fourier-transform, given
301 its adaptive time-frequency resolution (e.g. Dubechies, 1990; Farzampour et al., 2018a,b).
302 Figures 9(a)-(d) show the time-frequency maps of the transmitted P-wave signals related to the
303 received signals at t =25, 50, 75, and 100 hr. It should be noted that the time-frequency map at
304 t=25 hr was used as a baseline, while, the time evolution of frequency content (during the test)
305 can be inferred by comparing the time-frequency maps at different times. The time-frequency
306 map for P-wave signal recorded at t=25 hr is provided in Figure 89(a). It can be seen that the
307 energy of the higher frequency range (i.e. ~800 kHz) is higher than that of the lower frequency
308 range (i.e. ~200 kHz). This observation could be, in part, attributed to the fact that the fracture
309 aperture is relatively low and therefore, the contribution of the rock matrix in transmitting the P-
310 wave is more significant than the fractured volume, as confirmed by comparing the time-
311 frequency map of the transmitted P-wave through intact and fractured rocks. In addition, the
312 majority of the higher frequency portion of the transmitted P-wave arrives at t≈17 □Sec, while, a
313 small portion of the higher frequency range arrives at later times (at t≈27 and 32 □Sec).

314 In order to investigate the effects of fracture aperture alterations on the evolution of time-
315 frequency content, the transmitted P-wave signal at t=25 hr was subtracted from those at t=50,
316 75, and 100 hr. Then, the resultant signals were used as the input for wavelet transform to
317 generate the time-frequency maps and illustrated in Figures 9(b)-(d), implying that the energy of
318 the P-wave decreases over time. This indicates that the change in energy (i.e. amplitude) of P-
319 wave signal at an earlier time instance (e.g. t=50 hr) compared to those a later time instance (e.g.

320 $t=100$ hr) is more significant. On the other hand, as the test proceeds, the frequency partitioning
321 of the resultant P-wave signals is altered. In particular, the energy concentrated in the higher
322 frequency range decreases, and eventually, the lower frequency range has higher concentration
323 of energy compared to the higher frequency range. This indicates that the change in frequency
324 partitioning of P-wave signal is more significant at a later time instance (e.g. $t=100$ hr) compared
325 to an earlier time instance (e.g. $t=50$ hr).

326 **S-waves signals.** Following the same procedure for P-waves, time-frequency maps for
327 the S_1 - and S_2 -waves were developed and shown in Figures 9(e)-(h) and 9(i)-(l). Figure 9(e)
328 indicates that the higher amount of energy is stored in the lower frequency band (centered ~ 250
329 kHz) compared to the higher frequency band (centered ~ 650 kHz). Comparing the time-
330 frequency map for S_1 -wave with that of P-wave (see Figure 9(a)), it can be observed that the
331 difference between the lower and higher frequency bands is much smaller for S_1 -wave (~ 400
332 kHz) compared to that of P-wave (~ 600 kHz), an inherent characteristic of S-waves.

333 A comparison between the time-frequency map of S_1 -wave with that of S_2 -wave at $t=25$
334 hr (i.e. comparing Figure 9(e) with 9(i)) indicates that the higher and lower frequency bands are
335 centered around the same frequency, which are ~ 650 and ~ 250 kHz, respectively. This
336 observation indicates that both S_1 - and S_2 -waves have the same dominant frequencies. However,
337 the ratio of the peak spectral amplitude in the higher frequency band to that of lower frequency
338 band is lower for S_2 -wave compared to S_1 -wave. In addition, the spectral amplitudes for S_2 -wave
339 (see Figure 9(i)) is less than that of S_1 -wave (see Figure 9(e)). These differences between the
340 time-frequency maps of S_1 - and S_2 -waves might have been caused by various anisotropic
341 behaviors including (i) material anisotropy of the intact core retrieved from Blue Mountain

342 geothermal reservoir (Kamali-Asl et al., 2018d), (ii) anisotropic distribution of asperities in
343 different directions, and (iii) anisotropic flow paths (i.e. channelized flow) in different directions.

344 Similar to the procedure implemented for the P-waves, the signals recorded at $t=25$ hr for
345 cross-polarized S-waves were subtracted from those recorded at $t=50, 75,$ and 100 hr, in order to
346 better illustrate the evolution of the time-frequency maps caused by fluid-fracture surface
347 alterations. Figures 9(f)-(h) and 9(j)-(l) show the time-frequency maps of the resultant signals
348 (i.e. signal recorded at $t=25$ hr subtracted from those recorded at $t=50, 75,$ and 100 hr) for S_1 -
349 and S_2 -waves, respectively. As the time progresses, similar to P-waves, the maximum amplitude
350 of the $S_{1,2}$ -waves decreases, implying that the change in the energy (i.e. amplitude) of the
351 transmitted $S_{1,2}$ -waves is less significant at a later time instance (e.g. $t=100$ hr) compared to an
352 earlier time instance (e.g. $t=50$ hr). Also, similar to P-waves, the ratio of the spectral amplitude at
353 higher frequency band to that of lower frequency band becomes smaller at a later time instance
354 compared to an earlier time instance, which is more significant for the S_1 -waves compared to S_2 -
355 waves. This slight difference between the two cross-polarized S-waves could be attributed to the
356 anisotropy in (i) material, (ii) asperities distribution, and (iii) flow paths, as stated earlier.

357 **Displacement-Controlled Test (DCT)**

358 *Radial strains, ultrasonic velocities, amplitudes, and attenuations*

359 Figure 10(a) illustrates the evolutions of average radial strain and differential pore
360 pressure, indicating that there is a strong correspondence between radial strain and differential
361 pore pressure in DCT. The processes caused by fluid-fracture surface interactions alter fracture
362 permeability/hydraulic aperture, leading to increase/decrease in upstream pore pressure to

363 maintain the constant injection rate and consequently, ΔP increases/decreases accordingly. For
364 instance, as fracture permeability decreases, the upstream pore pressure intensifier adjusts (i.e.
365 increases) the upstream pore pressure (and subsequently ΔP) to maintain the constant injection
366 rate. Then, the increase in ΔP leads to increase in fracture aperture (to maintain the constant flow
367 rate), which in turn leads to the decrease in radial strain. The reverse correspondence between
368 fracture aperture and radial strain was also observed in PCT. For example, at the time intervals
369 with increase in ΔP (e.g. $t=48$ to 72 hr), the radial strain decreases, and vice versa.

370 Figure 10(b) shows the evolutions of the P-wave velocity and differential pore pressure,
371 implying a clear correspondence between P-wave velocity and differential pore pressure. When
372 ΔP increases, the P-wave velocity decreases (e.g. $t=20$ to 42 hr). This observation could be
373 attributed to the fact that as the fracture opens up, the contribution of the fractured volume
374 becomes more significant, and therefore, the P-wave velocity decreases. The direct
375 correspondence between fracture aperture and P-wave velocity was also observed in PCT. The
376 evolution of S_1 - and S_2 -waves velocities were not found to be sensitive to the changes in fracture
377 aperture, as shown in Figure 10(c), similar to the PCT.

378 Figure 11(a) shows the evolution of the normalized maximum amplitude of S_1 - and S_2 -
379 waves and differential pore pressure during DCT. It can be observed that there is a gradual
380 increase in the maximum amplitude of both S_1 - and S_2 -waves during the test, as the overall trend
381 of differential pore pressure is increasing and hence, the fracture aperture has been increased.
382 The direct correspondence between fracture aperture and maximum amplitude of S_1 - and S_2 -
383 waves were also observed in PCT. In addition, the evolution of the maximum amplitude of the P-
384 wave was not indicative of the changes in the fracture aperture, as was also observed in the PCT.

385 Figure 11(b) shows the evolutions of P-wave attenuation and differential pore pressure in DCT,
386 indicating sensitivity of P-wave attenuation to the alterations of fracture aperture/permeability, as
387 was also observed in Figure 8(a) for P-wave attenuation in PCT. The evolutions of S₁- and S₂-
388 waves attenuations were not found to be sensitive to the changes in fracture aperture, as was the
389 case for PCT.

390 *Time-frequency analysis*

391 **P-wave signals.** The time-frequency maps for P-, S₁-, and S₂-waves for representative
392 time instances of t=30, 60, 90, and 120 hr were generated by implementing wavelet transform.
393 The time-frequency maps at t=30 hr were shown to establish a baseline for the analysis of
394 changes in frequency content over the course of the test. The ultrasonic signals recorded at t=30
395 hr were subtracted from those recorded at t=60, 90, and 120 hr. Then, the resultant signals were
396 used as the input for the wavelet transform. Figure 12(a) shows the time-frequency map for the
397 P-wave signal recorded at t=30 hr, indicating higher and lower frequency bands centered ~800
398 and ~200 kHz, respectively, as also observed during the PCT. The higher frequency band has
399 higher energy (i.e. amplitude) compared to the lower frequency band, with very close amplitudes
400 compared to PCT. The higher frequency band arrives at three different time intervals centered at
401 ~18, ~25, and ~32 μ Sec, with the first arrival having the highest energy, while the lower
402 frequency band is more distributed from ~25 to 40 μ Sec, similar to what was observed in PCT.

403 Figures 12(b)-(d) illustrate the time-frequency maps of the resultant (subtracted) signals
404 related to t=60, 90, and 120 hr, indicating an increase in the energy (i.e. amplitude) of the
405 transmitted P-wave as time progresses. This observation is opposite to that of PCT, which can be
406 attributed to the different mechanisms of conducting the two types of flow-through test. More

407 precisely, in PCT the upstream and downstream pore pressures are constant and the flow rate
408 changes over time. However, in DCT, the downstream pore pressure and upstream injection rate
409 are set as constant and the upstream pore pressure is continuously adjusted to maintain the
410 prescribed constant injection rate. Consequently, the decrease in the energy of the transmitted P-
411 wave in a later time compared to an earlier time over the course of the PCT can be attributed to
412 the lower flow rate (i.e. lower fracture aperture). While, the increase in the energy of the
413 transmitted P-wave in a later time instance (e.g. $t=120$ hr) compared to an earlier time instance
414 (e.g. $t=60$ hr) over the course of the DCT can be attributed to the higher differential pore pressure
415 (i.e. higher fracture aperture). The frequency partitioning of the resultant signals did not indicate
416 tangible changes over time, as opposed to that of the PCT. This could be attributed to the fact
417 that the volume of the fracture remains almost the same.

418 **S-waves signals.** Time-frequency maps for S_1 - and S_2 -waves are illustrated in Figures
419 12(e)-(h) and 12(i)-(l), respectively. Figures 12(e) and 12(i) show the time-frequency maps of S_1 -
420 and S_2 -waves at $t=30$ hr, indicating higher and lower frequency bands centered ~ 650 and ~ 250
421 kHz, respectively, which are similar to those in PCT. The contribution of the higher frequency
422 band is more significant for S_1 -wave, while, the contribution of lower frequency band is more
423 significant for S_2 -wave, similar to PCT. The energy (i.e. amplitude) of the transmitted S_1 -wave is
424 slightly more than that of S_2 -wave, as also observed in PCT.

425 Figures 12(f)-(h) and 12(j)-(l) illustrate the time-frequency maps for the resultant signals
426 (i.e. ultrasonic signal at $t=30$ hr subtracted from those at $t=60, 90,$ and 120 hr) for S_1 - and S_2 -
427 waves, respectively. It can be observed that, comparing time-frequency of the resultant signal at
428 $t=120$ hr with that of $t=60$ hr, the change in energy (i.e. amplitude) becomes more pronounced as

429 the test proceeds, as observed for P-wave. This observation is in contrast to those of the PCT,
430 which can be attributed to the difference in mechanisms of conducting these two modes of flow-
431 through-fracture tests, as explained earlier. Comparing Figures 12(f), 12(g), and 12(h) (or
432 equivalently 12(j), 12(k), 12(l)), it can be inferred that the frequency partitioning of the S_1 - and
433 S_2 -waves does not change over time, similar to that of P-waves in DCT, and in contrast to that of
434 all ultrasonic waves in PCT.

435 CONCLUSION

436 In this study, the sensitivity of P- and S-wave ultrasonic signatures (e.g. velocity,
437 frequency content, amplitude, and attenuation) to the alterations of hydraulic properties, due to
438 fluid-fracture surface interactions, were investigated. Pressure- and displacement-controlled
439 flow-through-fracture tests were performed on an artificially-fractured reservoir phyllite
440 specimen. The ultrasonic P-, S_1 -, and S_2 -waves and radial strain were measured during flow-
441 through-fracture tests to evaluate the correspondence between evolution of fracture aperture to
442 those of ultrasonic signatures.

443 The results suggested that ultrasonic signatures can potentially be used as a proxy for
444 flow-induced fracture aperture evolution. An increase in fracture aperture led to a decrease in
445 radial strain, with a more pronounced change in radial strain when the change in fracture aperture
446 is significant. The P-wave velocity and attenuation, and the maximum amplitude of S_1 - and S_2 -
447 waves can be used as indicators of fracture aperture change in fractured formations. In particular,
448 a decrease in fracture aperture led to (i) increase in the P-wave velocity, (ii) decrease in the P-
449 wave attenuation, and (iii) increase in the maximum amplitude of cross-polarized S-waves.
450 However, the evolutions of S_1 - and S_2 -waves velocities/attenuations and the evolution of

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451 maximum amplitude of P-wave were not indicatives of the changes in flow
452 rate/aperture/permeability.

453 The time-frequency maps of the transmitted ultrasonic P-waves revealed higher and
454 lower frequency bands of ~800 and ~200 kHz, while those of both S-waves were ~650 and ~250
455 kHz. For pressure-controlled test, the frequency partitioning of the transmitted ultrasonic signals
456 (P-, S₁-, and S₂-waves) showed a slight transition from higher frequencies to lower frequencies
457 as the test progressed, while those of displacement-controlled test did not show changes in
458 frequency partitioning. The energy of the transmitted ultrasonic waves showed lower increase in
459 energy content as the test progressed for pressure-controlled test, while those of displacement-
460 controlled test indicated higher increase in the energy content.

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REFERENCES

462 Acosta-Colon, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., & Nolte, D. D., 2009, Laboratory-scale study of
463 field of view and the seismic interpretation of fracture specific stiffness: *Geophysical*
464 *Prospecting*, **57**(2), 209-224.

465 Batzle, M. L., Han, D. H., & Hofmann, R., 2006, Fluid mobility and frequency-
466 dependent seismic velocity—Direct measurements: *Geophysics*, **71**(1), N1-N9.

467 Caulk, R. A., Ghazanfari, E., Perdrial, J. N., & Perdrial, N. (2016). Experimental
468 investigation of fracture aperture and permeability change within Enhanced Geothermal
469 Systems. *Geothermics*, *62*, 12-21.

470 Cook, N. G., 1992, Natural joints in rock: mechanical, hydraulic and seismic behaviour
471 and properties under normal stress: *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining*
472 *Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts*, **29**(3), 198-223.

473 Daubechies, I., 1990, The wavelet transform, time-frequency localization and signal
474 analysis: *IEEE transactions on information theory*, **36**(5), 961-1005.

475 Faoro, I., Elsworth, D., & Candela, T., 2016, Evolution of the transport properties of
476 fractures subject to thermally and mechanically activated mineral alteration and
477 redistribution: *Geofluids*, **16**(3), 396-407.

478 Farzampour, A., Kamali-Asl, A., & Hu, J. W., 2018a, Unsupervised identification of
479 arbitrarily-damped structures using time-scale independent component analysis — Part I: *Journal*
480 *of Mechanical Science and Technology*, **32**(2), 567-577.

Geophysics

- 481 Farzampour, A., Kamali-Asl, A., & Hu, J. W., 2018b, Unsupervised identification of
482 arbitrarily-damped structures using time-scale independent component analysis — Part
483 II: *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, **32**(9), 4413-4422.
- 484 Gu, B., *Interface Waves on a Fracture in Rock*, Ph.D. Thesis, University of California,
485 Berkeley, 1994.
- 486 Kamali-Asl, A., Ghazanfari, E., Perdrial, N., & Bredice, N., 2018a, Experimental study
487 of fracture response in granite specimens subjected to hydrothermal conditions relevant for
488 enhanced geothermal systems: *Geothermics*, **72**, 205-224.
- 489 Kamali-Asl, A., Ghazanfari, E., Newell, P., & Stevens, M., 2018b, Elastic, viscoelastic,
490 and strength properties of Marcellus Shale specimens. *Journal of Petroleum Science and*
491 *Engineering*. **171**, 662-679.
- 492 Kamali-Asl, A., Ghazanfari, E., Hedayat, A., & Deering, L., 2018c, Investigation of
493 static/dynamic moduli and plastic response of shale specimens. *International Journal of Rock*
494 *Mechanics and Mining Sciences*. **110**, 231-245.
- 495 Kamali-Asl, A., K-C, B., Foroutan, M., Ghazanfari, E., Cladouhos, T. T., & Stevens, M.,
496 2018d, Stress-strain response and seismic signature analysis of phyllite reservoir rocks from Blue
497 Mountain geothermal field: *Geothermics*, **77**, 204-223.
- 498 Knight, R., Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., Slater, L., Atekwana, E., Endres, A., Geller, J., ... &
499 Straley, C., 2010, *Geophysics at the interface: Response of geophysical properties to solid-fluid,*
500 *fluid-fluid, and solid-solid interfaces: Reviews of Geophysics*, **48**(4).

Geophysics

501 Mavko, G., Mukerji, T., & Dvorkin, J., 2009, The rock physics handbook: Tools for
502 seismic analysis of porous media: Cambridge university press.

503 Mukerji, T., & Mavko, G., 1994, Pore fluid effects on seismic velocity in anisotropic
504 rocks. *Geophysics*, **59**(2), 233-244.

505 Müller, T. M., Gurevich, B., & Lebedev, M., 2010, Seismic wave attenuation and
506 dispersion resulting from wave-induced flow in porous rocks—A review: *Geophysics*, **75**(5),
507 75A147-75A164.

508 Nolte, D. D., Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., Beachy, J., & Ziegler, C., 2000, Transition from the
509 displacement discontinuity limit to the resonant scattering regime for fracture interface
510 waves: *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, **37**(1-2), 219-230.

511 Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., Myer, L. R., & Cook, N. G., 1990, Transmission of seismic waves
512 across single natural fractures: *Journal of Geophysical Research (Solid Earth)*, **95**(B6), 8617-
513 8638.

514 Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., & Morris, J. P., 2000, Single fractures under normal stress: The
515 relation between fracture specific stiffness and fluid flow: *International Journal of Rock
516 Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, **37**(1-2), 245-262.

517 Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., DePaolo, D. J., & Pietraß, T., 2015, Controlling subsurface fractures
518 and fluid flow: a basic research agenda: USDOE Office of Science (SC)(United States).

519 Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., & Nolte, D. D., 2016, Approaching a universal scaling relationship
520 between fracture stiffness and fluid flow: *Nature communications*, **7**, 10663.

Geophysics

521 Roy, S., & Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., 1995, Interface waves propagating along tensile fractures
522 in dolomite: *Geophysical Research Letters*, **22**(20), 2773-2776.

523 Roy, S., & Pyrak-Nolte, L. J., 1997, Observation of a distinct compressional-mode
524 interface wave on a single fracture: *Geophysical Research Letters*, **24**(2), 173-176.

525 Saltiel, S., Selvaduari, P. A., Bonner, B. P., Glaser, S. D., Ajo-Franklin, J. B., 2017,
526 Experimental development of low-frequency shear modulus and attenuation measurements in
527 mated rock fractures: Shear mechanics due to asperity contact area changes with normal
528 stress: *Geophysics*, **82**(2), M19-M36.

529 Sayers, C. M. (2013). The effect of kerogen on the elastic anisotropy of organic-rich
530 shales: *Geophysics*, **78**(2), D65-D74.

531 Sone, H., & Zoback, M. D., 2013a, Mechanical properties of shale-gas reservoir rocks—
532 Part 1: Static and dynamic elastic properties and anisotropy: *Geophysics*, **78**(5), D381-D392.

533 Sone, H., & Zoback, M. D., 2013b, Mechanical properties of shale-gas reservoir rocks—
534 Part 2: Ductile creep, brittle strength, and their relation to the elastic modulus: *Geophysics*, **78**(5),
535 D393-D402.

536 Standard, A. S. T. M. D5777-00, 2011, “Standard Guide for Using the Seismic Refraction
537 Method for Subsurface Investigation,” ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.

538 Wang, Z., 2001, Fundamentals of seismic rock physics: *Geophysics*, **66**(2), 398-412.

Geophysics

539 Witherspoon, P. A., Wang, J. S., Iwai, K., & Gale, J. E. (1980). Validity of cubic law for
540 fluid flow in a deformable rock fracture. *Water Resources Research*, 16(6), 1016-1024.

541 Yu, Y., Zhang, J., & Zhang, J. (2009). A modified Brazilian disk tension
542 test. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 46(2), 421-425.

543 Zoback, M. D., 2010, Reservoir geomechanics: Cambridge University Press.

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